

CURE MONITORING OF EPOXY STRUCTURAL ADHESION USING LAMB WAVES AND THE DISCRETE WAVELET TRANSFORM

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ABSTRACT

Epoxy adhesives have extensive applications in the aerospace industry. In this study, the curing behaviour of pre-impregnated epoxy adhesive was monitored using guided ultrasonic Lamb waves. These waves were excited and recorded using ultrasonic transducers. This study aims to analyze the recorded Lamb wave data using the discrete wavelet transform (DWT). A 5-level DWT was performed on the recorded ultrasonic signals. The approximation and detail coefficients of the signals were analyzed to extract the evolution of the degree of cure (DOC) as a function of time. The results were then validated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The results have shown that the DOC obtained from the DWT matches the one obtained using DSC. This method was able to detect the start time and end time of the curing process. The correlation between the two DOCs was found to be $R^2 = 0.68$ indicating that ultrasonic Lamb waves can be used as a real time monitoring method for the degree of cure of a material during the manufacturing process.

Keywords: Cure monitoring, Degree of cure, Lamb waves, Signal processing, Discrete Wavelet transform.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cure monitoring is the study of the curing reaction of a material in real-time. This process has been more frequently applied in industrial applications since it can guarantee the quality and the mechanical properties of the finished product. In polymer chemistry, curing refers to the toughening of a polymer solution by cross-linking its polymer chains at high temperatures. Cure monitoring can be done through various methods such as thermal imaging, differential scanning calorimetry, and ultrasonic methods. Cure monitoring through guided ultrasonic Lamb waves is a widely used method that assesses the group velocity of the waves propagating between the actuator and the sensor [1]. Named after the mathematician Horace Lamb, Lamb waves are elastic waves that travel on the surface of solid structures plates, rods, and shells. Since the 1990s, the understanding and utilization of Lamb waves have advanced significantly, especially in the field of non-destructive testing. These waves play a crucial role in assessing material integrity without causing damage. Lamb waves propagate through plate-like structures in two possible configurations: symmetric or the S_0 mode and antisymmetric or the A_0 mode. The propagation of the Lamb waves in an isotropic plate that is unbound in the x and y directions is described by the following set of simplified equations [2]:

$$\frac{\omega^4}{C_T^4} = 4k^2 q^2 \left[1 - \frac{p \tan\left(\frac{ph}{2} + \gamma\right)}{q \tan\left(\frac{ph}{2} + \gamma\right)} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$p^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{C_L^2} - k^2 \quad (2)$$

$$q^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{C_T^2} - k^2 \quad (3)$$

where γ represents the phase of the S and A wave modes for values of 0 and $\frac{\pi}{2}$, respectively, h is the plate's thickness, ω is the angular frequency and k is the wave number. C_L and C_T are respectively the longitudinal and

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transverse velocities of the Lamb wave in the bulk material. Lamb waves are complex vibrational waves that propagate parallel to the test surface throughout the thickness of the material. Their propagation depends on the material properties, frequency, and thickness, making them valuable for various practical applications in material science.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Cure monitoring using ultrasonic Lamb waves

Ultrasonic testing using guided Lamb waves is an extensively researched tool in the field of composite materials. Applications of these waves include testing the structural integrity of the composite material and in-process cure monitoring of the composite during the manufacturing process. Lamb waves are used to identify various viscoelastic stages of the manufacturing process. As the material cures, it undergoes various transformations such as gelation, vitrification, and glass transition. Monitoring these changes is crucial to ensure the composite's quality and performance.

Mahfoud et al [1] studied the curing reaction of carbon fiber prepregs using guided ultrasonic Lamb waves. The prepregs were cured in the oven by ramping the temperature from 25°C to 70°C and then 120°C. The cure monitoring process was done by using two Teflon layers in which two piezoelectric sensors were sandwiched. This sensing system is placed directly in contact with the laminate as it can give a very good output signal of the Lamb wave propagation through the material. To excite the Lamb waves, a five-peak sinusoidal Hanning window was generated. The amplified signal to the actuator has a 160V peak-to-peak amplitude with a certain frequency of 70 kHz. The oscilloscope was used to collect the data at a sampling rate of 1 sample/10mins. The group velocity and the amplitude of the anti-symmetric mode A_0 was estimated from the distance between the transmitter and the sensor which is covered by the time of flight of the anti-symmetric Lamb wave mode. All three curing parameters: minimum viscosity, gelation, and vitrification were detected in both generated graphs. The results of the ultrasonic testing were validated against the dynamic mechanical analysis test where the curing parameters were also identified. This study has proved the potential of using a reusable Teflon film as a sensing medium for the in-situ cure monitoring of prepreg carbon fiber. It also proposed shortening the cure cycle of the tested prepreg by 1 hour. The carbon fiber prepreg with a shortened cure cycle was tested for its tensile strength using a universal testing machine. The experimental results showed that by reducing the cure cycle by 1 hour, the cure behavior of the prepreg is shifted by 1 hour without significant change in its mechanical properties.

2.2 Digital signal processing of ultrasonic Lamb waves

One of the major challenges in ultrasonic cure monitoring is relating the recorded signal to the actual physical changes happening during the curing [3]. To help interpret the complex signals obtained from Lamb waves, various signal processing methods have been implemented. Recent methods include Wavelet transforms, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), and the Hilbert transform (HT). Hilbert transform is used for the time domain processing, the Fourier transform is used for the frequency domain processing, and the Wavelet Transform is used to analyze both time and frequency domains simultaneously.

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is an algorithm that efficiently computes the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of a sequence or its inverse (IDFT). In this method, the observed Lamb wave amplitude-time recording is converted into recordings of the wave numbers at discrete frequencies [4]. The FFT has found application mostly in structural health monitoring (SHM) applications. For instance, Alem et.al [5] used the FFT and time of flight (TOF) techniques to estimate the size and location of damage instantaneously without the need for prior baseline signals. Regarding cure monitoring, the FFT is underrepresented in the literature. Such studies often favor other digital signal processing methods such as the Hilbert Transform and the Wavelet Transform.

The Hilbert Transform (HT)

The Hilbert transform is a valuable tool in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). It aids in damage detection and localization by analyzing data from distributed sensors. The Hilbert-Huang transform (HHT) is one of the most

popular signal processing methods in SHM. This filter combines empirical mode decomposition with the Hilbert spectral transform, making it adaptive for analyzing stationary, non-stationary, and transient signals in SHM. Shahri et.al [6], used the HT to characterize the failure mechanisms in laminated composite materials. The HT method was applied to correlate acoustic emission signals with their corresponding failure modes. The experimental analysis focused on glass/epoxy laminated composites subjected to an end notch flexure test which simulates delamination. By analyzing the phase angle of the Hilbert transform, the frequency range associated with damage mechanisms occurring at different loading stages was identified. Additionally, scanning electron microscopy provided visual insights into the cracked surfaces. The results demonstrated the practical applicability of the proposed acoustic emission-based HT method for characterizing damage mechanisms in laminates, with strong agreement between the findings and microscopic images.

The HT finds valuable applications in field of cure monitoring of composite materials. It improves the process of cure monitoring by revealing valuable insights into the curing process and its effects on the quality of composite materials. In [3], the authors investigated the usage of the Hilbert transform for extracting the instantaneous features of the Lamb wave response. For this purpose, symmetric carbon fiber prepreg laminates were manufactured in a (0/90)_s stacking sequence. Two piezoelectric sensors were attached to the surface of the prepreg, which were operating in a pitch-catch mode. The input signal has the following characteristics: 185 kHz excitation frequency, 10V peak to peak amplitude and a 5-cycle sine pulse modulated by a Hanning window. The data acquisition was performed on an oscilloscope with 50 Ms/s (Mega samples/seconds). The recorded signals were decomposed and then filtered using the HT from which the frequency and amplitude of the signals were extracted. The results given by the HT exhibited two noise heavy regions and a structural region in which the characteristics of the signal reflect the physical changes in the curing reaction. The changes in the frequency and amplitude in the structural region are directly correlated with the change in the material viscosity. This allows for the identification of the major curing regions: minimum viscosity, gelation, and vitrification.

The Wavelet Transform

The usage of wavelet transform-based methods to analyze ultrasonic signals is rather popular. However, it is underutilized in cure monitoring studies that use ultrasonic-guided Lamb waves. The wavelet transform provides a method to analyze the time and frequency domains simultaneously [7]. A wavelet, $\psi(t)$, is a rapidly decaying, wave-like oscillation. It enables the representation of data across multiple scales, making it suitable for various applications in signal processing. Generally, it is a function characterized by its zero average, scale parameter s , and time shift u [8]:

$$\Psi_{us}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \psi\left(\frac{t-u}{s}\right) \quad (4)$$

The wavelet transform $Wf(u, s)$ of a signal $f(t)$ is computed by the inner product of $f(t)$ with a wavelet atom:

$$Wf(s, u) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t) \psi^*\left(\frac{t-u}{s}\right) dt \quad (5)$$

Where ψ^* represents the complex conjugate of the wavelet atom. These wavelets, when combined with shifts of a real-valued low-pass scaling function $\phi(t)$, form an orthonormal basis expansion for the one-dimensional continuous time signal $f(t)$. This finite energy signal can be therefore decomposed into wavelets and scaling functions as follows [9]:

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c(n) \phi(t-n) + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} d(j, n) 2^{j/2} \psi(2^j t - n) \quad (6)$$

This decomposition is referred to as the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) of the continuous time signal $f(t)$. The scaling coefficients $c(n)$ and wavelet coefficients $d(j, n)$ are computed via the inner products:

$$c(n) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \phi(t-n) dt \quad (7)$$

$$d(j, n) = 2^{j/2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \psi(2^j t - n) dt \quad (8)$$

Application of the Wavelet Transform and its variants in Lamb wave analysis

The wavelet transform has various applications in the non-destructive testing (NDT) field of material science. In particular, it had extensive utility in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) and Cure Monitoring applications.

In SHM studies, the nature of the recorded signal allows the relaxation of the filter constraints. The filter does not need to be time invariant as the Lamb waves recorded in SHM studies do not change over time. This allows for the researcher to use any of the variants of the wavelet transform. For instance, recent damage detection studies have employed the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) as a tool to analyze Lamb wave signals. Saqib, Zheng, and Kaihong [10] estimated structural damage using the CWT. The ultrasonic sensing configuration consisted of PZT actuators and sensors mounted on a platelike structure. The plate was discretized into several points and the likelihood of damage at each grid point is directly determined by the coefficients of the CWT. By applying the CWT coefficients, which are based on the Gabor wavelet, to signals scattered by damage, an envelope was created for each actuator-sensor pair. The results have proven that, by using the CWT, damage can be detected and localized using only the signals detected from the damaged plate. This method eliminates the need to have a baseline or undamaged signal in damage detection studies. In a similar study, Zheng et al. [11] used the CWT to detect the damage in the plate based on the time of flight of the second harmonic Lamb wave. The bump wavelet functions were effectively used to detect the components of the second harmonic Lamb wave. The time of flight was then extracted from the signal using the Gabor wavelet function.

SHM studies can also employ the DWT to analyze Lamb wave signals. In [8], the DWT was used to extract the relevant features from noisy ultrasonic Lamb wave signals. The experimental setup consisted of a steel plate where artificial damage was created. Ultrasonic Lamb waves were generated at a frequency of 1.9 MHz received by a digitizing oscilloscope and amplified by a band-pass filter between 0.9 and 5.5MHz. Images of the artificial defects were generated based on the computed wavelet coefficients. The results showed that analyzing the real ultrasonic signals yielded more precise damage detection. Using the DWT method to analyze Lamb wave signals permits the extraction of the relevant features in the time-frequency domain without needing to return to the time domain. This is an advantage that the DWT has over more traditional methods of analysis, such as the Fourier transform.

The usage of the wavelet transform has not been extensively studied in cure monitoring applications. The study conducted by Koichi and Ogi [12] presented a method for evaluating the degree of cure of a carbon fiber prepreg based on the CWT. 10 layers of CFRP prepreg were laid up for the cure monitoring experiment. The ultrasonic testing setup consisted of 3 PZT sensors, where one acted as the actuator and the other acted as the receiver. The CFRP was cured in an electric oven by ramping the temperature from 25°C to 160°C at a rate of 2°C/min and then holding the temperature at 160°C for 5hrs. The CWT and HT were used to obtain the viscoelastic properties of the prepreg (gelation and vitrification) during its curing cycle. The group velocity and the attenuation of the Lamb waves relate to the degree of cure by the following equation:

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{1}{L_2 - L_1} \log \frac{A_1 \sqrt{L_1}}{A_2 \sqrt{L_2}} \quad (9)$$

Where L_1 , L_2 are the distances between the actuator and the first and second receivers, respectively. A_1 and A_2 represent the peaks of the CWT envelope for each sensor, respectively. The results of the ultrasonic method were validated experimentally using dynamic mechanical analysis. The material properties generated by this method were proven to be useful in modeling the curing process using numerical simulation.

In cure monitoring, the Lamb wave signals are affected by the evolution of the temperature as a function of time and material properties. Hence the filter applied in processing these signals needs to be time invariant and be able to detect features in higher dimensions. Therefore, the Dual-Tree Complex Wavelet transform (DTCWT) was proposed as a more suitable digital signal processing technique than the traditional DWT in this domain [13]. Holst et al. [13] monitored the curing process of a thin plate of CFRPs using guided Lamb waves. The prepreg was heated linearly to 160°C by increments of 2°C/min starting at room temperature. The piezoelectric actuators were excited by a single pulse square wave within the frequency interval of 150kHz to 400kHz with a frequency step size of 2kHz. The recorded signals were then analyzed using a variant of the DTCWT. This method is more robust in cure monitoring due to its almost time invariance by using two parallel wavelet transforms. This method allows estimation of the degree of cure of the prepreg by detecting the change in the resonance frequency, and the energy transmitted by the dominant wavelet. For instance, the vitrification of the prepreg was captured by noting the time at which the energy transmitted begins to increase. In addition, the attenuation of the energy transmitted is an indication of the final degree of cure which is indicated by the stop in change of the transmitted energy. The degree of cure was then determined by the energy of the dominant wavelet coefficient and its corresponding resonance

frequency. The multi-sensor Lamb wave approach ensures more homogeneous curing and facilitates the detection of defects using non-destructive methods.

This study aims to test the viability of the wavelet transform in the digital signal processing of Lamb wave signals. We are interested in the cure monitoring experiment of epoxy adhesives. The wavelet transform will be used to estimate the degree of cure of the adhesive as a function of time. These results will be validated against the experimental of the differential scanning calorimetry.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Experimental setup

In the cure monitoring experiment, 7 layers of epoxy adhesive film (XPREG-XA120) were stacked to form a plate with a thickness of 1 mm. The plate has the dimensions of $32 \times 35 \text{ cm}^2$. Figure 1 shows the uncured adhesive plate and the two PZTs glued directly on top of it. The actuator and the sensor are labeled as A and S, respectively. The PZTs are disc-shaped PZT-5J material type with 0.5 mm thickness, 7 mm diameter, and have 320°C Curie temperature. The PZT actuator is excited using a five-peak sinusoidal signal multiplied by a Hanning window. The PZT sensor feeds the data into an oscilloscope which is recording it every five minutes. The epoxy plate is cured by ramping from room temperature up to 120°C with a heating rate of $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, then holding isothermal curing conditions for one hour at the said temperature, then cooling naturally.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of epoxy cure monitoring

3.2 Signal processing

The Lamb wave signals collected from the cure monitoring experiment will be analyzed using a variant of the Wavelet transform. Since Lamb waves transport kinetic energy, the degree of cure $\alpha(t)$ of the prepreg will be determined by the wavelet coefficients. The signal processing analysis was done using Python and the wavelet transform package Pywavelets [14].

Optimal wavelet selection

In wavelet transform analysis, the choice of the mother wavelet or the basis function determines the accuracy and efficiency of the results. By choosing the optimal mother wavelet, important features of a Lamb wave signal such as the time of flight can be extracted on both time and frequency domains. The selection of the mother wavelet is usually done using Shannon's entropy. Shannon's entropy is a measure of randomness in a closed system which also reflects the energy concentration of a signal along with the uncertainty associated with it. For a process $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n]$, the simplified Shannon's entropy is given by [15]:

$$S(P) = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \ln p_i \quad (10)$$

A library L , containing Daubechies, Haar, and Symlet wavelets. The selection process starts by choosing a mother wavelet M ($M \in \{L\}$) and applying it to each of the 33 signal samples $x_i(t)$. The mother wavelet is selected to have the minimum entropy of all the ones in the library L . In practice, it is useful to calculate the energy-to-entropy ratio of the signal. The signal energy-to-entropy ratio (EER) is a measure that can be used to assess the quality or characteristics of a signal. EER is calculated according to the following equation:

$$EER[n] = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^l |x_k|^2}{S_p[n]} \quad (11)$$

Where n is the number of the signal samples ($0 \leq n \leq 33$) and l is the length of each signal ($0 \leq l \leq 2000$).

DWT

The 33 obtained Lamb wave signals were run through a 5-level DWT decomposition using the chosen mother wavelet. The input signal $x[n]$ is split equally and then passed through a low-pass filter $h_0[n]$ and a high pass filter $h_1[n]$. The output of the low pass branch is the approximation coefficients $A_1[n]$ while the output of the high pass branch is the detail coefficients $D_1[n]$. In a multilevel DWT analysis the approximation coefficients $A_i[n]$ are reintroduced to the low pass-high pass filter bank. In this study, a 5-level DWT analysis was performed, and the outputs of interest are A_5, D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4 and D_5 .

Signal energy analysis

Using the 33 Lamb wave signals recorded in the curing process, the energy of the wavelet detail $d(j, n)$ is calculated and scaled with respect to the first measurement taken. The energy of a wavelet detail $d(j, n)$ is then determined as follows:

$$E_n({}^s d_i) = \frac{1}{E_s({}^s d_1)} \sum_{k=0}^n |{}^s d_i[k]|^2 \quad (12)$$

in which i is the index of the current measurement. The degree of cure is then calculated using the following equation:

$$\alpha(t) = 1 - E_n({}^s d_i) \quad (13)$$

3.3 Validation

To validate the results, the curing behavior of the epoxy prepreg is investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Isothermal DSC scans were done by heating the epoxy sample using the curing cycle provided by the manufacturer. The samples were heated from 25°C up to a maximum temperature of 120°C. This temperature was held for 60 mins, after which the sample was cooled at different rates (5, 3°C/min) down to 25°C. The degree of cure $\alpha(t)$ is obtained by integrating the area under the heat flow graph obtained by DSC. The graph of the degree of cure α_{DSC} , obtained by differential scanning calorimetry, will be compared with the one generated by the wavelet transform α_{DWT} to validate this ultrasonic cure monitoring method.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Optimal mother wavelet selection

The tested wavelet library L , consisted of Daubechies (db), Haar, and Symlet (sym) wavelets. The notation using the wavelets library is given by the following equation:

$$L = [db1, db2, db3, sym4, sym20, haar] \quad (14)$$

Where $db1, db2$ and $db3$ represent the Daubechies wavelets with 1, 2 and 3 vanishing moments, respectively, $sym4$ and $sym20$ represent the Symlet wavelets with 4 and 20 vanishing moments, respectively and $haar$ represents the Haar wavelets. The collected Lamb wave signals were arranged in a 2000×33 matrix where each signal represents a sample n at time t . The average EER for each mother wavelet across all 33 signal samples is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Average signal energy-to-entropy ratio for the tested mother wavelets

Mother wavelet	EER
<i>db1</i>	21.5×10^3
<i>db2</i>	238×10^3
<i>db3</i>	1.17×10^6
<i>sym4</i>	1.6×10^6
<i>sym20</i>	5.9×10^6
<i>haar</i>	21.5×10^3

Furthermore, the variation of the EER across the sample number n is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Energy-to-entropy ratio as a function of the sample number n for each of the tested mother wavelets

From the results of Table 1, we can see that the "sym20" mother wavelet has the highest average EER of 5.9×10^6 . Therefore, this wavelet contains high amounts of energy per unit of Shannon's entropy. This translates into the mother wavelet's ability to concentrate energy effectively and to capture important features of the Lamb wave signal while minimizing noise.

4.2 DWT of the Lamb wave signal

Figure 3 shows the level 5 approximation and detail coefficients for the first Lamb wave signal recorded during the cure monitoring experiment. The detail coefficients reflect the main A_0 wavelet packet recorded in the main signal present at $400 \leq k \leq 800$ effectively by filtering out all the low-frequency components of the signal. Important features such as the energy carried by the A_0 waves can be extracted from the detailed coefficients of the DWT. Applying the 5-level DWT to a signal that appears to be holding little to no information resulted in a good localization of the A_0 wave packet as shown in Figure 4. In a typical Lamb wave analysis, the signal shown in Figure 4 is disregarded because it is too noisy, and thus no relevant features can be extracted from it.

Figure 3: Original signal, approximation coefficients, and detail coefficients of the signal captured at $n = 0$

Figure 4: Original signal, approximation coefficients, and detail coefficients of the signal captured at $n = 10$

4.3 Signal energy analysis

Figure 5 shows the degree of cure extracted from the signal energy of the detail coefficients for each signal sample. From this analysis, we can see that curing begins at $t = 30 \text{ mins}$ and ends at $t = 60 \text{ mins}$. The shape of the graph matches the typical degree of cure graphs found in the literature [13].

Figure 5: Degree of cure of the prepreg calculated from the ultrasonic Lamb wave signals

From Figure 5, we can see that the degree of cure is approximately 0 for the first 30 minutes of the experiment. Indicating that the curing reaction begins at $t = 30mins$. The degree of cure then reaches the value of 1 at $t = 70 mins$ signifying the end of the curing reactions.

4.4 Validation of the degree of cure

The results of the ultrasonic tests were validated against the analysis of the DSC test. Figure 6 shows the degree of cure of the prepreg obtained from the DSC test. The correlation between the degree of cure obtained from the ultrasonic test and the degree of cure obtained from DSC analysis was good with a correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.68$.

Figure 6: Degree of cure of the prepreg calculated from differential scanning calorimetry

The start time and end time of the curing reaction were also validated. As shown in Figure 6, the curing reaction starts at $t = 30mins$ and ends at $t = 70mins$. These results agree with the start and end times found from the DWT analysis of the Lamb wave signals.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the application of the DWT in ultrasonic testing was studied. Lamb wave signals were recorded during the curing process of the 7-layer XPREG-XA120 prepreg epoxy adhesive film. A five-level DWT was applied to the 33 recorded signals. The results have shown that the DWT amplifies the desired features of the analyzed signal since it was able to condense and filter noisy Lamb wave signals. Furthermore, the energy of the wavelet's detail coefficients was used to calculate the degree of cure of the prepreg as a function of time. This analysis was then validated using differential scanning calorimetry. The results have shown the ability of ultrasonic Lamb waves to monitor the curing reaction. Future studies need to further explore the utility of DWT and its variants in cure monitoring applications. Real wavelets have been proven to have several disadvantages when processing a particular signal. Future work can tackle the usage of more complex variants of the DWT such as the DTCWT to measure the degree of cure of the prepreg during the manufacturing process.

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